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Controlling the molecular diffusion in MOFs with the acidity of monocarboxylate modulators

Isabel Abánades Lázaro^{a,*}, Catalin Popescu^b and Francisco G. Cirujano^{a,*}

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The catalytic performance of metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) is related to their physicochemical properties, such as particle size, defect-chemistry and porosity, which synthetic control can be potentially achieved by coordination modulation. By combining PXRD, ¹HNMR, FT-IR, N₂ uptake measurements we have found insights that the different types of defects (missing linker or missing clusters consequence of the spatial distribution of missing linkers, and the combination of both) could be controlled by the type of modulator employed. We show that the molar percent of defects, either as missing linkers or as part of missing cluster defects, is related to the modulator's acidity and subsequent incorporation into the UiO-66 structure. Modulators with strong acidity and small size result in a considerable defect induction that causes an increase in the external surface area and mesopore volume, beneficial for the ring-opening of epoxides with amines, using UiO-66 defect-modulated MOFs as heterogeneous catalysis.

Introduction

Coordination modulation of Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) ¹ – highly stable, porous hybrid structures composed of metal clusters linked by multidentate organic ligands ^{2–4} – has emerged as a defect engineering tool to enhance their applications and has received notable attention in the last decade. ^{5–7} Defects in Zr MOFs were first reported in 2011, ⁸ with thermogravimetric analysis of modulated Zirconium UiO-66 MOFs revealing a linker deficiency, which was further agreed by EXAFS showing a loss of ligands in the first Zr coordination shell, compensated by monotopic ligands, so-called modulators. Modulators are typically monotopic ligands that are introduced during MOFs synthesis and compete with the multitopic linkers for the metal nucleation sites. ⁹ Coordination modulation was first reported in 2008 for Zn MOFs, ¹⁰ applied to Zr MOFs in 2011, ¹¹ and has boosted the number of reported MOFs ever since. ⁹ The modulator can be attached to the metal clusters of the resultant structure as capping (size-control) and/or defect-compensating ligands, providing functionality to the framework. ^{12–17} In turn, modulators can also act as crystal growth promoters through control of the acidity of the synthesis media without permanent attachment to metal clusters, increasing the particle size and enhancing crystallinity. ¹¹ The addition of modulators enables fine-tuning of properties

such as size, ¹⁸ functionality ^{15,19} and defect chemistry, ^{6,14} which are themselves related to changes in MOFs polydispersity, ²⁰ mechanical, thermal, and chemical stabilities, ^{21,22} porosity ¹⁴ and density of open metal sites, ^{23,24} beneficial for several applications such as heterogeneous catalysis. ^{24–28}

Zr MOFs are the benchmark materials regarding defect chemistry, due to the high stability of the frameworks towards the reduction of the cluster's coordination number. ^{29–31} Among them, the UiO series of MOFs ³² (UiO stands for University i Oslo), with UiO-66 (Zr-terephthalate) represented in **Figure 1**, can reduce its coordination number from 12-connected to 8, resulting in missing clusters consequence of the spatial distribution of missing linkers within the framework. ^{30,33} To the best of our knowledge, the spatial organisation of missing linkers into point defects (non-extended linker deficient metal sites) or missing clusters is still not fully understood and controlled, with controversial studies found in the literature. ²⁹ In fact, while missing clusters have been proposed to be the only type of defect, ^{14,29} HR-TEM has recently shown the co-existence of different types of defects, represented in **Figure 1**: ordered missing linkers from the 12-connected parent *fcu* 4[Zr₆(μ₃-O)₄(μ₃-OH)₄L₆] network into a *bcu* 8-connected 4[Zr₆(μ₃-O)₄(μ₃-OH)₄L₄(Mod)₄] net in which all the BDC ligands are removed from the parent structure projected along the <001> axes, 8-connected missing cluster *reo* phase 3[Zr₆O₄(OH)₄L₄(Mod)₄] in which one cluster and its connected linkers (L) are missing, with linker being compensated by modulators (Mod), and 8,4-connected *scu* net 3[Zr₆(μ₃-O)₄(μ₃-OH)₄L₃(Mod)₆] of missing cluster defects (**Figure 1**). ³³ By means of formic acid (FA) modulation, the authors visualized that under their FA modulated conditions the missing linker domains predominate over the missing clusters, with FA defect-compensating modulators attached Zr positions. Recent reports also show missing linker defects organising into other defective phases

^a Instituto de Ciencia Molecular (ICMol), Universitat de València, Catedrático José Beltrán Martínez nº 2, 46980 Paterna, Valencia, Spain.

^b CELLS–ALBA Synchrotron, E-08290 Cerdanyola del Valles, Barcelona, Spain.

† These authors contributed equally.

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such as missing cluster defects in the UiO-66 *hcp* network with $Zr_{12}(\mu_3-O)_8(\mu_3-OH)_8(\mu-OH)_6$ nodes (paired Zr_6O_8 nodes bridged by OH groups).^{34–36}

Defects play an active role in the chemical reactivity of MOFs, and hence their catalytic activity.^{23,24} Recent reports have shown that defective tetravalent metal sites affect the conversion and selectivity of catalytic processes of industrial relevance, such as the activation of carbonyl groups in the synthesis of biomass-derived platform molecules, biodiesel and other high added value molecules.^{37–39} Point defects at crystalline positions interrupt the periodicity of the framework, increasing the accessibility to the coordinatively unsaturated metal sites that interact with the substrates. The presence of defects is often interconnected with the porosity and particle size (nucleation and crystallisation kinetics),⁴⁰ which have a clear incidence on the molecular transport in and out of the active sites. In the particular case of zirconium-based MOFs, the defective metal-oxo clusters have Lewis/Brønsted acidity which can be controlled by the use of modulators (e.g. monocarboxylic acids), mineral acids, water, zirconium precursors, temperature, time, etc.) during synthetic and post-synthetic conditions.^{23,24,27,41}

Figure 1 Ideal UiO-66 phase (fcu) and different defective phases due to missing clusters (reo, scu) or linkers (bcu).

Although the catalytic performance of the defect-containing metal-oxo clusters is related to the bulk physicochemical properties of the materials, studies that enclose both detailed rationalisation of properties based on the synthetic conditions and the interrelation with the MOFs' catalytic performance are imperative to provide insights into the control of the interrelation between synthesis, properties and function, which will lead to the design of catalytic MOFs of outstanding

performance in relevant catalytic/adsorption solid-based processes. In particular, heterogeneously catalysed synthesis of industrially relevant compounds through C-C and C-N bond-forming processes, such as fine chemicals and pharmaceuticals, are recent examples where MOFs can bridge state-of-the-art homogeneous catalysts with robust reusable solid catalysts.^{39,42,43}

Herein, we study the effect of modulator's acidity and molecular size in UiO-66 properties in relation to its catalytic performance in the transformation of epoxides into amino alcohols via MOF-catalysed C-N bond formation,^{36,44–47} aiming to provide insights that will lead to the design of highly catalytic MOF systems based on their controlled properties. We have chosen UiO-66, a robust system that allows for precise control of its chemical reactivity through defect engineering.²⁹ The already demonstrated acidic properties of this catalytic platform enable the transformation of many organic compounds through heterogeneous catalytic processes taking place at the nodes of the UiO framework.^{24,27,48,49} When part of the structure is disrupted by the attachment of monocarboxylates, a more open framework is generated, thus favouring accessibility to the active sites in the form of open metal sites (coordinatively unsaturated sites), with sufficient stability due to the high connectivity of the MOF nodes.^{14,50}

Results and discussion

In order to induce defects into UiO-66 structure, we have introduced 10 equivalents (with respect to the linker) of well-known defect promoting modulators. We have maintained a fixed excess of linker compared to the metal (1.5 equivalents) to reduce particle size and enhance defect promotion by speeding the metal-linker complexation and subsequent nucleation equilibria.⁴⁰ We have chosen Benzoic Acid (BA), Formic Acid (FA) and Trifluoro Acetic Acid (TFA) as modulators, paying special attention to their pK_a (4.2, 3.7 and 0, respectively) and molecular size (See S.2 in the supporting information for detailed synthetic conditions). Note that in the MOF structures FA corresponds to formate, TFA to trifluoroacetate and BA benzoate. Recent reports have shown that the pK_a of acetic acid derivative modulators is inversely related to the induction of defects in UiO-66,¹⁴ whereas the higher defect promoting activity of benzoic acid in comparison with its pK_a analogue, acetic acid, under stoichiometric metal-linker ratios has been attributed to its molecular size, more similar than benzene dicarboxylate.⁵¹

Figure 2a shows that besides the appearance of sharp Bragg peaks from the UiO-66 framework in the Powder X-Ray Diffraction (PXRD), the BA and TFA modulated samples show the existence of a weak broad band (2 theta = 2–3.5), indicated with an arrow in **Figure 2a**. This band, considered indicative of the presence of superlattice peaks,¹⁴ is more significant for the TFA modulated sample, whereas it was no apparent upon FA modulation despite it having a lower pK_a than BA. (See S.3.1 in the supporting information). The *reo* phase has been reported as a broad band at low reflection angles when measured with conventional PXRD, whereas recent reports show that both the

8-connected *reo* and 8,4-connected *scu* missing cluster phases simulated PXRD have new reflection bands (100) and (110) at low angles that are absent in both the pristine MOF and the *bcu* net of ordered missing linkers.³³ The modulator incorporation into the framework was analysed by combining NMR and FT-IR profiles. NMR (Table 1 and S.3.2 in the supporting information) revealed that the modulator (BA, FA, TFA) incorporation in mole percent (mol%) is inversely related to their pK_a (Figures S6 and S7 in the supporting information). However, FA coming from the decomposition of DMF during MOF synthesis also incorporates in BA and TFA modulated frameworks, although to a less extent than upon its direct addition, but resulting in a

higher number of total monocarboxylate ligands (total modulator) attached to the framework (Figure S8 in the supporting information). FA co-incorporation compensates for the charge balance upon the replacement of ditopic linkers by BA and TFA modulators, possibly making the missing cluster defects more favourable. FT-IR profiles, represented in Figure 2b (See S.3.3 in the supporting information), show characteristic vibration bands of the modulators such as C-F₃ stretching at *ca.* 1195 and 1140 cm⁻¹ or C-F bending at *ca.* 791 cm⁻¹, but the free carboxylate vibration bands are not present due to the modulator attachment to the Zr cluster.

Figure 2 a) Stacked PXRD of modulated UiO-66 in comparison with simulated UiO-66 and simulated *Reo* phase. b) FT-IR profiles of modulated UiO-66 in comparison with pristine UiO-66. c) TGA profiles of modulated UiO-66 with metal residue normalized to 100%. d) Representation of the molar percent of missing linkers in $Zr_6O_4(OH)_4(L)_x(FA)_{x_{NMR}}(Mod)_{z_{NMR}}(OH)_z(H_2O)_z$ as a function of the modulator's pK_a , where missing linkers correspond to 6-*x*, being *x* determined by the combination of NMR analysis of the acid-digested MOF with TGA.

Gravimetric analysis of the thermal decomposition profiles of the MOFs (See S.3.4 in the supporting information), represented in Figure 2c, revealed a high defectivity in agreement with the high incorporation of monotopic modulators determined by NMR, being the molar percent of missing linkers directly related to the modulator's acidity (Figure 2d) due to their incorporation to the oxo-metallic nodes (See S.3.4 and Figures S11-18 in the supporting information for detailed explanations of the mathematical models).⁵² TGA revealed *ca.* 4.71, 4.56 and 4.26 linkers (6 for the pristine MOF) in the molecular formula $Zr_6O_4(OH)_4(L)_x(FA)_y(Mod)_z(OH)_d(H_2O)_d$

for BA, FA and TFA respectively, corresponding to *ca.* 21, 24 and 29 molar% of missing linkers (Table 1). In the *reo* phase, one cluster and its connected linkers (33.3 %molar percent) are removed from the pristine $4[Zr_6(\mu_3-O)_4(\mu_3-OH)_4L_6]$ MOF upon replacement by monotopic monocarboxylate modulators (bidentate) or by a combination of bidentate and monodentate monotopic modulators (i.e. OH) that coordinate 8 positions in the unit cell with paired neutral species (i.e. water, solvent), resulting in $3[Zr_6O_4(OH)_4(L)_4(Mod)_4]$ and derivative structures.^{14*30}

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Table 1 Characterisation data extracted from NMR and TGA techniques.

Technique	NMR		TGA				
	MOD ^a /L	FA ^b /L	L ^c / Zr ₆	MOD / Zr ₆	FA / Zr ₆	Wt% Zr /DH MOF	ML ^d %
BA@UiO-66	0.19	0.22	4.71	0.84	0.91	47.6	21.5
FA@UiO-66	0.29	0.29	4.56	1.33	0.00	52.3	24.1
TFA@UiO-66	0.42*	0.18	4.26	0.92	1.80	54.0	29.0

^aMod refers to the modulator, ^bFA refers to formic acid, ^cL refers to linker and ^dML refers to missing linker.

To rule out the influence of particle size in external surface area ⁵³ we have measured the particle size of the three modulated-MOF samples by Scanning Electron Microscopy (See section **S.3.5** in the supporting information) using ImageJ software to analyze the particle size distributions. The average particle size has no statistical significance between sets, as shown in **Figure 3a**. This indicates that size will not play a role in assessing differences in their porosity and catalytic activity. ⁵³ Indeed, analysing the average particle size as a function of modulator's incorporation (**Figure S22** in the supporting information) rules out the influence of the particle size in the external surface area and mesopore volume.

The N₂ adsorption and desorption isotherms (see **S.3.6** in the supporting information), represented in **Figure 3b**, indicate that the addition of modulators increases porosity, with S_{BET} of ca. 1390 m²g⁻¹ upon TFA and FA modulation Vs. 1200 m²g⁻¹ for pristine UiO-66 (**Table 2**, **Figure S24** in the supporting information). The increase of porosity rules out the possibility of linker deficiency coming from a metal-rich particle surface. However, the less defective sample (BA) has a smaller S_{BET} than the pristine MOF. This could be due to the higher volume and weight of TFA and BA modulators in comparison to FA, ⁵¹ and to the fact that TGA revealed DMF obstructed in the pores of BA and TFA samples, but not of FA (See **S.3.4** in the supporting information for assessment of coordinated and obstructed DMF). However, the external surface area and the mesopore volume (**Table 2**) are both proportional to the molar percent of missing linkers, as represented in **Figure 3c**, which was previously assessed to be related to the modulator's acidity, while there is no relation to the average particle size (**Figure S25** in the supporting information). Although it is known that external surface area is related to particle size for small nanoparticles, given that the average particle size of this samples has no statistical differences, together with defects

playing an important role on the pore size and opening explains that the external surface area is directly related to the materials defect concentration. High external surface areas are beneficial for catalytic applications, where interface phenomena, defective metal sites and intra-crystalline diffusion play a major role, in addition to the micropore area, offering a higher number of active sites available at the surface of the nanoparticles. ^{54,55}

The pore size distributions (PSD) represented in **Figure 3c** reveal changes in the pore size distributions from the reported tetrahedral (8 Å) and octahedral (11 Å) pores ³² that indicates nanoregions of missing clusters defects for TFA and BA modulated samples, which exhibited significant pores at ca. 16 and 19 Å, consistent with the reported simulated PSD of the *reo* phase.⁵⁶ However, while TFA@UiO-66 has completely lost the original pore at 8 Å (and the volume of the 11 Å pore is 3 and 6 times smaller in magnitude than the 16 and 19 Å pores respectively), BA@UiO-66 conserves the pristine MOF pores, which have a similar magnitude to the new ones. FA@UiO-66 presents a different PSD, with no tetrahedral 8 Å pore (as TFA) but new pores at ca. 13 and 15 Å, being the latter the most significant of all. Although its bigger pore is similar to the simulated *reo* phase (ca. 16 Å), ⁵⁶ its smaller size together with the absence of the *reo* 19 Å pore indicates, in great agreement with the absence of a broad band at low angles in the PXRD, that missing clusters are not the most prevalent defects in FA@UiO-66. In addition, the simulated accessible surface area (1360 / 1612 m²g⁻¹) and pore volume (0.503 / 0.557 cm³g⁻¹) for UiO-66 with 9 linkers out of (4.5 out of 6) compensated by FA or OH- respectively is similar to the experimental porosimetry values of FA@UiO-66 (**Table 2**), with 9 out of 12 linkers calculated by the combination of TGA and NMR, with missing linkers compensated by a combination of FA and OH-. ⁵⁷

Figure 3 a) Statistical box chart of the particle size distributions of modulated UiO-66, showing 25% and 75% quartiles, the average size and the standard distribution. b) N_2 adsorption and desorption isotherms of modulated UiO-66. c) Representation of the external surface area and mesopore volume of modulated UiO-66 as a function of the molar percent of missing linkers. d) Pore size distribution of modulated UiO-66.

Table 2: Characterisation data extracted from N_2 adsorption/desorption isotherms

Sample	$S_{\text{BET}} / S_{\text{MICRO}} / S_{\text{EXT}} (\text{m}^2/\text{g})$	$V_{\text{micro}} / V_{\text{meso}} (\text{cm}^3/\text{g})^a$		$V_t (\text{cm}^3/\text{g})^a$
BA@UiO-66	1042 / 929/113	0.362	0.071	0.433
FA@UiO/66	1393 / 1226/167	0.494	0.121	0.615
TFA@UiO-66	1389 / 1165/224	0.431	0.164	0.595

^a V_{micro} was calculated with t-plot model with Harkins and Jura thickness curve based on the BET surface areas. V_{total} was calculated at $P/P_0 = 0.9$ and $V_{\text{meso}} = V_{\text{total}} - V_{\text{micro}}$.

Although TGA provides very good calculations of the molecular formula of the materials, it cannot differentiate between the type of defects (missing linkers and/or missing clusters and their topology).²⁹ Due to the previously discussed PXRD, TGA and PSD data, we postulate that BA and TFA induce missing cluster defects upon incorporation, with partial compensation by FA, while the missing cluster contribution for FA modulation is less significant. The MOF exhibits *ca.* 29% of missing linkers upon modulation with highly acidic TFA, close to the 33% of missing

linkers for the pure **reo** phase, and its PSD matches well with **reo** simulations, suggesting exclusively missing cluster defects. BA@UiO-66 presents 21% of missing linkers, leading to a smaller degree of missing clusters. However, the preservation of its micropore structure suggests pairing missing linkers that are not part of missing cluster defects. In contrast, when only FA is added in the absence of other modulators, it incorporates to the MOF structure compensating for missing linker defects, which spatial distribution does not favour the formation of

missing cluster defects for the studied conditions (excess of linker), at least not in a significant manner in the form of nanoregions, as indicated by PXRD and PSD. The differences in the type of defects induced are not related to the modulator's pK_a , but could be a consequence of their molecular size: steric hindrance due to bigger molecular size favours the attachment of FA (from the decomposition of DMF) and OH/H₂O pairs in close proximity instead of linkers. Although this study encloses 3 modulators, further studies on the relation between the modulator's molecular size vs. pK_a , and the formation of different defective phases in UiO-type MOFs are undergoing.

Overall, characterization reveals that while the particle size can be maintained by fixing an excess of linker, the molar percent of defects, their type and distribution could be tuned by the modulator's choice. The molar percent of defects and the external surface area are related to the modulator's acidity and subsequent incorporation, but its molecular size seems to play a more important role in determining their spatial distribution, resulting in missing linker defects for FA and co-existence missing linkers and missing clusters for TFA and BA, with its consequent impact in the pore size distribution.

Figure 4 a) Conversion of cyclohexene oxide (left axis, red bars) and selectivity to the resulting amino alcohol (right axis, red circles) in the presence of (Zr)UiO-66 catalysts after 8 h (b) or 24 h (c) prepared with three different monocarboxylate modulators (BA = benzoic acid, FA = formic acid, TFA = trifluoroacetic acid).

At this point, we investigated the impact of defect-modulated MOF properties (Zr sites associated with defectivity and related porosity features) in the activation of oxygen and nitrogen-containing substrates (e.g. epoxides, alcohols and amines).⁵⁸ The resulting Zr open metal sites due to the presence of the different modulators allow the transformation of amines and epoxides into pharmaceutically relevant functional molecules like amino alcohols (i.e. adrenaline). Hence, we have studied the inter-relation between the defective materials' properties and their catalytic performance in the straightforward synthesis of β -amino alcohols through regioselective ring-opening of oxiranes (epoxides) with amines, represented in **Figure 4a**, by reacting cyclohexene oxide with aniline, which was performed at room temperature in EtOH with and without MOF for 24 hours (See **S.4** in the supporting information for detailed conditions).

While the non-catalysed reaction between aniline and cyclohexene oxide at room temperature has a 3% conversion after 24 hours, the defective MOFs are active catalysts of the desired C-N bond formation, reaching a *ca.* 80% conversion for TFA-modulated UiO-66 after 24 hours and *ca.* 59% after 8 hours, as represented in **Figures 4b** and **c**, and tabulated in **Table S6** of the supporting information.

Conversion and selectivity are related to MOF defectivity, among other inter-related properties. **Figures 4b** and **c** show that the pK_a of the modulator is inversely proportional to the conversion and directly proportional to the selectivity towards the addition of aniline (instead of the alcohol solvent, which may act as a nucleophile in the presence of more defective MOFs). As previously discussed, the modulator's pK_a is related to its incorporation and the resultant framework's defectivity - a lower pK_a results in a higher amount of deprotonated species that are more effective in capping the Zr₆-oxoclusters - and so, the more defective the MOF, the higher the catalytic conversion (**Figure 5a**). Replacing linkers by modulators results in the opening of the framework, leading to higher mesopore volumes and external surface areas. This results in more accessible Zr active sites, which are available for the activation of the reaction substrates. Moreover, bulkier modulator molecules, like benzoic acid, occupy more space in the MOF cavities, which results in an important decrease of porosity in comparison to light monocarboxylates, i.e. formic or trifluoroacetic acid. Thus, the influence of missing linkers on the textural properties of the crystals (improving the diffusion of reactants during the ring-opening of cyclohexene epoxide) is the cause of its improved catalytic performance, as illustrated in **Figure 5b** and **c**. Thus, being acidity, defectivity, mesopore volume and external

surface area inter-related properties, all are proportional to modulated UiO-66 catalytic activity in the order TFA>FA>BA, as illustrated in **Figure 5** and **Figures S28-S31** in the supporting information. The PXRD patterns of the spent materials are similar to the as-prepared MOFs, indicating no damage to the structure (**Figure S33** in the supporting information). Additionally, **Figure S34** shows that the high performant TFA@UiO-66 maintains its catalytic activity and selectivity during 4 reaction cycles.

The increase in conversion is notable if we consider that previous literature reports show a 40% conversion in the ring-

opening of epoxides after 24 hours at 55°C for UiO-66 with 1.75 missing linkers out of 12,⁵⁸ whereas our conditions are at room temperature and reach up to 80% conversion with ca. 4 out of 12 missing linkers. To put our results in context, we have calculated the TONs per Zr site associated to defects in the coordination-modulated MOFs reported here with that of other Zr-MOFs reported in the literature. Assuming ca. 30 wt.% of Zr associated to defective clusters, the TON of these sites is 8, which could be competitive with the TON of 2-20 obtained with benchmark Zr-MOFs for the same reaction studied here.^{44,59}

Figure 5 Relation between cyclohexene oxide conversion percent after 24 hours and the structural and textural properties of the UiO type MOFs: modulator acidity (a), linker defects (b), pore volume (c), external surface area.

Conclusions

We have shown the versatility of the MOF-modulated approach in tailoring the porosity of the final material. The pK_a of monocarboxylate molecules (e.g. benzoic, formic and trifluoroacetic acids) used as modulators of the crystal growth of zirconium carboxylate frameworks is key in controlling the degree of defects in the crystal. The concentration of defects in the form of missing terephthalate linkers that have been exchanged by the monocarboxylate is inversely proportional to the pK_a of the modulator. Through defect engineering of the framework, the mesoporosity and external surface area can be tailored to expose a higher number of Zr acid sites readily available to interact with reactants involved in catalytic processes. Both cyclohexene oxide and aniline diffusion are favoured for the TFA-modulated MOF, which shows improved textural (higher porosity) and, thus, catalytic properties (higher conversion in the ring-opening of epoxides).

Although this study encloses 3 modulators, we encourage MOF researchers to closely look at the relation between modulator's molecular size and pK_a , with the formation of different defective phases in UiO-type MOFs. This investigation also suggests that the formation of either missing clusters or missing linkers and their distribution does not affect the materials catalytic properties drastically, with overall replacement of linkers (in either of the defective phases) and its relation with the material's porosity driving catalytic performance.

Author Contributions

The manuscript was written through the contributions of all authors. All authors have approved the final version of the manuscript.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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